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Dyscalculia and intervention tools

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Abstract

This article focuses on dyscalculia, a learning disorder affecting mathematical skills, without being related to the child's intelligence. In modern education, the diagnosis of dyscalculia is becoming more reliable with the use of technological tools. Children with this disorder often struggle with understanding mathematical concepts, performing calculations, and recognizing mathematical relationships. However, early diagnosis and appropriate intervention can significantly contribute to enhancing their learning abilities. Technology, such as digital games and educational software, has proven to be effective in enhancing the mathematical skills of students with dyscalculia.

Keywords: Dyscalculia; ICT; Constructivist Theory; Working Memory; Virtual Reality; Artificial Intelligence; Mobile Applications

1. Introduction

It is estimated that the prevalence of dyscalculia ranges from 3 to 6% of the global population. Research shows that it often appears in twins and in families with a history of similar difficulties (Tsombolis, 2017).

The term "dyscalculia" comes from the Greek word "dys" and the Latin word "calculia." There are various terms used for mathematical learning difficulties. Ladislav Kosc (1974) introduced the term "Developmental Dyscalculia," while Koontz and Berch (1996) used the term "Numerical Learning Difficulties." Hich prefers the term "Specific Numerical Difficulties," and Temple and Sherwood (2002) use the term "Mathematical Facts Disorder" (Butterworth, 2008, as cited by Drigas et al., 2016).

Kosc (1974) described developmental dyscalculia as a disorder of mathematical abilities with a genetic or congenital basis in specific parts of the brain, without being accompanied by general intellectual dysfunction (Khing, 2016).

There is a direct correlation between dyscalculia and working memory difficulties, specifically the ability to memorize numbers in a specific sequence. According to Geary (2010), there are three cognitive components in mathematical learning difficulties (Mathematics Learning Disabilities - MLD):

- Retrieval of numerical data from long-term semantic memory
- Execution of procedures for solving numerical problems
- Representation and interpretation of spatial representations of mathematical information (Geary, 2010, as cited by Drigas et al., 2016).

Learning difficulties, such as dyscalculia, persist throughout life, but with early diagnosis and appropriate intervention, students can show significant improvement (Course, 2006, as cited by Drigas et al., 2016).

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Children with learning difficulties in mathematics may exhibit the following characteristics according to Tzivinikou (2015):

- Struggle to understand and solve mathematically described word problems.
- Have trouble managing money and performing everyday transactions.
- Struggle to organize and process mathematical problems in writing.
- Cannot recognize and follow logical sequences in mathematical steps.
- Have difficulty understanding the sequence of events and steps in a problem.
- Cannot verbally describe the mathematical processes they use.
- Struggle with measurement, learning numerical data, and performing calculations.
- Cannot effectively apply mental strategies to solve mathematical problems.

2. ICT and Education

Modern technologies related directly or indirectly to computers are internationally known as Information and Communication Technology (ICT). According to Kumar (2008), ICT is a general term that encompasses any device or application for communication. This includes radio, television, mobile phones, computers, network hardware and software, satellite systems, and various related services and applications such as videoconferencing and distance learning.

According to Komi (2004), the phases of introducing Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) into education are four:

- The period of educational technology and teaching machines (before 1970): During this first period, educational technology focused on the use of teaching machines and audiovisual media. Radio and television were widely used as educational tools, aiming at direct teaching in the classroom, school broadcasts, and educational programs in general.
- The computer approach (1970-1980): The 1970s were characterized by the introduction of computers into education. This approach involved the integration of computers into school classrooms, facilitating the learning of basic computer skills.
- Computers as both a medium and a subject of education (1980-1989): In the 1980s, computing became both a tool and a subject of education. Students were taught how to use computers and software while also using computers as learning tools in various subjects.
- Information and communication technologies as teaching and learning tools (after 1990): From the 1990s onward, ICTs became an integral part of teaching and learning. The use of the internet and computers enabled the development of interactive and personalized learning methods, while simultaneously facilitating communication and collaboration between students and teachers.

3. The Use of ICT in Children with Special Learning Difficulties

The integration of Information and Communication Technologies in education has proven crucial for supporting students, especially those with special learning difficulties. Research has shown that ICT provides opportunities for increased participation in the educational process and promotes interactive experiences that encourage active student engagement (Benmarrakchi, Kafi & Elhore, 2016). Furthermore, the use of ICT can enhance students' autonomy, giving them more control over the learning process and reducing their reliance on the teacher (Vlassopoulou & Papadimitriou, 2006).

Specifically, new technologies empower students' self-esteem and motivation by providing additional opportunities for practice and interaction, helping them develop a positive image of themselves and the learning process (Alexander-Passe, 2006). This approach can be particularly beneficial for students with learning difficulties, as it enables them to fully participate in the social context of the classroom and improve their social skills (Cooper, Smith & Upton, 2002).

Finally, we stress the significance of all digital technologies in the field of education and in learning difficulties training, which is highly effective and productive and facilitates and improves assessment, intervention, and educational procedures via mobile devices that bring educational activities everywhere [141-144], various ICT applications that are the main supporters of education [145-167], and AI, STEM, Games and ROBOTICS that elevate educational procedures to new performance levers [168-174]. Additionally, the development and blending of ICTs with theories and models of

metacognition, mindfulness, meditation, and emotional intelligence cultivation [175-199], accelerates and improves more the educational practices and results, particularly in learning difficulties.

4. ICT and Constructivist Theory

The integration of ICT in education has brought about significant changes in the way we teach and learn. The adoption of ICT is supported by various learning theories, with constructivist theory playing a central role (Chaudhary, 2018).

Constructivist learning theory posits that knowledge is not simply transmitted from the teacher to the student, but is actively constructed by the student through interaction with the environment and peers. Piaget and Vygotsky are two of the most important theorists in constructivism. Piaget focused on the cognitive development of individuals, while Vygotsky emphasized the importance of social interaction in learning (Yang & Kwok, 2017; Wang, 2008).

ICT can support constructivist learning with tools and platforms that facilitate active participation and collaboration among students. Online learning platforms such as Moodle, and collaborative tools such as discussion forums and blogs, enable students to collaborate and exchange ideas, enhancing the process of knowledge construction (Wang, 2008).

Vygotsky's theory of social constructivist learning highlights the importance of social interaction and collaborative education. ICT can facilitate this interaction through social networks and online platforms that enable collaboration and knowledge exchange among students (Yang & Kwok, 2017).

The use of ICT in education also involves the application of scaffolding techniques that provide guidance and support to students during their learning journey. Scaffolding can be provided either by individuals (such as teachers) or systems (such as learning software and platforms). These techniques help students gradually and safely develop their skills and knowledge (Yang & Kwok, 2017; Wang, 2008).

The integration of ICT in education, supported by the theories of constructivist learning, offers significant benefits for both students and educators. Students have the opportunity to actively participate in learning, collaborate with their peers, and develop their knowledge and skills in a more efficient and interactive manner. Educators, on the other hand, can use ICT to provide more personalized and flexible support to their students, enhancing the overall educational experience (Wang, 2008).

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5. Intervention Tools

5.1. Computer-Based Tools

Brunda and J. Bhavithra developed "**Computer-Assisted Instruction (CAI)**", which includes E-Learning and Adaptive E-Learning. These tools aim to teach mathematical concepts such as number names, counting, and number comparison through interactive software. The system adapts to the level of each student, offering different difficulty levels and providing auditory feedback. The project targets children up to 8 years old with dyscalculia, enhancing their cognitive and numerical skills (Drigas et al., 2016).

Lontrup et al. (2012) developed and tested a product that examines the potential for improving the understanding of mathematical equations by students in grades 7–10 through the use of physical objects. Students face difficulties with the complexity of equations and their rules. The product consists of six **Sifteo cubes** and a **computer application**. The cubes detect when they are placed side by side, when tilted, and when their screen is pressed. The student selects the first equation in the app, which is displayed on the cubes. Students move the cubes to solve the equation, with various support tools such as color indicators, automatic point changes, and automatic calculations, which gradually decrease as they progress. The results show that physical interaction helps students better understand equations, boosting their confidence and reducing frustration. Colors and elements from gamification were used to support this process (Lontrup et al., 2012).

The research of Ginsburg et al. (2015) proposes six cognitive principles for designing and evaluating mathematical software, using the software **MathemAntics** as an example. These principles target preschool and early school-aged children and include (Drigas et al., 2016):

- Engage children in cognitively and mathematically appropriate activities.
- Develop effective models for representing abstract ideas.
- Encourage accurate and effective strategies.
- Identify and eliminate errors and misconceptions.
- Design appropriate physical interaction.
- Integrate narratives and stories with mathematical concepts.

To apply these principles, the MathemAntics software uses various media and technologies such as interactive graphics, animations, immediate feedback, adaptive activities, and gamification (Ginsburg et al., 2015).

The educational software Round with Value is designed for teachers, offering materials and lesson plans to organize their teaching according to the needs of students. The program lasts 23 hours and is suitable for teaching euro coins to children with severe learning difficulties (Institute of Educational Policy, 2022).

5.2. Multimedia Tools and the Web

Hasselbring et al. (2005) conducted a study on the use of technology for learning mathematics in children with dyscalculia. They developed the software **FASTT**. FASTT Math uses unique features to help users connect facts with their answers through interactive software. The findings showed that when the software is used daily for about 10 minutes, most students with math difficulties can develop fluency in a single operation after approximately 100 sessions. Therefore, the key to success seems to lie in consistent use of the program. As expected, students who used the program regularly performed much better than those who were irregular users (Hasselbring et al., 2005).

The game **The Number Race** is an adaptive educational software designed to address dyscalculia. Its goal is to improve children's numeracy skills through interactive exercises that adapt to each player's skill level. It provides a fun and effective means of developing basic numerical skills and overcoming difficulties related to dyscalculia. Results showed that this software application could be effective in addressing dyscalculia, at least for children aged 7-8 years and younger (Wilson, 2006).

Another study was conducted by Räsänen et al. (2009), examining the effectiveness of digital intervention for children with dyscalculia or low numeracy skills. Thirty children from preschool and early school age were randomly divided into two groups. The first group used **The Number Race**, while the second group played **Graphogame-Math**. **The Number Race** focuses on teaching number sense and addition through an interactive game, while **Graphogame-Math** uses auditory stimuli to reinforce learning of quantitative distinctions. Both groups were trained with the games for three weeks, 10-15 minutes daily (Drigas et al., 2016). The results showed that children achieved significant improvement in number comparison, but the result did not generalize to counting or arithmetic. However, the feedback provided by the tools allows the child to adjust their actions in relation to the goal (Räsänen et al., 2009).

Calcularis is a computer-based educational program created by Käser et al. to help children with dyscalculia. The study involved thirty-two German-speaking students (2nd-5th grade) in Switzerland who had difficulties learning mathematics. The children used the program for 20 minutes a day, five days a week, for 6-12 weeks. **Calcularis** consists of 10 different types of games that leverage number representations, visualization of numbers using colored blocks, arithmetic operations, and word problems (Drigas et al., 2016). With variations of the numbers used in the games, 81 different exercise types (difficulty levels) are created. Users start the program from the lowest level and progress according to their abilities (Käser et al., 2011).

The project by Laurillard et al. (2009) involved the development of digital interventions for children with dyscalculia. They designed and tested the programs **Dots2-Digits** and **Dots2Track**, which aimed to help students connect dots with digits. They studied the software and created an online environment for the creation of an interactive website, offering teachers access to information and discussion forums. According to the educators, the use of digital games allows students to practice more compared to traditional teaching (Drigas et al., 2016).

5.3. Virtual Reality

A study by Marcus Vansconcelos and his collaborators examined how a **virtual environment** affects children with dyscalculia. The *Tom's Rescue* virtual environment was used, which includes 18 educational games designed to incorporate fun elements and educational goals. These games cover skills such as number recognition, number sequences, number comparison, and the four basic arithmetic operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division). The study was conducted in São Paulo, Brazil, and involved 26 children with dyscalculia, with an average age of 8 years, attending 2nd grade. The children were randomly assigned to two groups: the experimental group, which interacted with the virtual environment and the specially designed games, and the control group, which participated in remedial teaching using traditional methods. The experimental group attended one-hour sessions, twice a week, for 5 weeks. The results showed that the use of the virtual environment significantly improved the children's math skills and increased their motivation. The computer was found to be a more engaging and fun tool compared to traditional teaching methods, providing a more encouraging and effective learning environment (Drigas et al., 2016).

Plerou and Vlamos explored how an **interactive virtual environment** influences students' ability to solve algorithmic problems. The study involved 46 students aged 15-16 from the first year of a Vocational Education School in Corfu. The students were divided into two equal groups: the control group, where students worked on traditional algorithmic thinking problems in class with 25 minutes of available time, and the interactive assessment group, where students worked on the same problems in an interactive virtual environment in a computer lab, with 15 minutes of available time plus additional time for reading instructions. The results showed that students who worked in the interactive virtual environment performed better on less complex algorithmic thinking tasks compared to the traditional group. The use of the virtual environment helped students better understand the basic concepts of algorithms and improve their performance on less complex problems, offering a more engaging and creative approach to mathematical thinking (Plerou et al., 2013).

In 2022, Lu, Cho, and Zou published a study examining how virtual reality can improve working memory. The results were positive, showing that participants found this learning method effective and innovative. Virtual reality games can benefit children with learning difficulties, including those facing problems with geometry. Studies have shown that games like *Minecraft* and *Geometry Explorer* can help develop spatial skills and improve understanding of geometric concepts (Drigas & Galitskaya, 2023).

Geometry Explorer uses a virtual environment to enhance students' understanding of three-dimensional (3D) geometric concepts through interaction with 3D shapes. Designed as a game, it aims to make learning geometry more engaging and interactive for students. In this game, users must adjust the dimensions of the 3D shapes to achieve specific volume goals. Users earn points for achieving the goals quickly, and a leaderboard motivates them to improve their performance. Through this approach, the system strives to make the process of learning volume calculation formulas and spatial perception more enjoyable and appealing (Lai et al., 2016).

A study conducted in 2022 by Su et al. in Taiwan utilized the *Virtual Reality Immersive Learning Mathematics Geometry System (VRMLGS)*, a virtual reality system specifically designed for teaching geometric concepts. The study involved 40 second-year high school students who were divided into two equal groups: a control group and an experimental group. The study lasted five weeks and began with a pre-test to assess the students' prior knowledge of geometric concepts. During the study, the experimental group used the virtual reality system to learn geometric concepts, while the control group was taught using traditional methods. At the end of the study, a post-test was conducted to evaluate the knowledge the students gained. The results showed that after using the virtual reality technology, students were able to perform learning tasks and acquire all the essential knowledge of basic mathematical geometry through course activities. It significantly improved the learning experience, interest, and self-confidence of the students (Su et al., 2022).

In 2021, a study was conducted to examine the effect of virtual reality on the teaching and learning of geometry. The system used was *NeoTrie VR*, a dynamic 3D virtual reality geometry software that allows for the creation, visualization, manipulation, and dynamic interaction with three-dimensional geometric objects and models. The research was conducted in four classrooms in Spain and Poland, with students aged 10-15 years. The students were divided into groups and followed a learning model combining traditional teaching methods and the use of NeoTrie VR. The results showed that the use of NeoTrie VR allowed students to improve their spatial sense, reasoning skills, argumentation, interest, and motivation (Rodríguez, 2021).

The study by Syafril et al. (2021) aimed to design and evaluate the effectiveness of the **VirGO (Virtual Geometry)** mobile application, which is based on augmented reality, for learning mathematics. The development of the VirGO application was carried out in three stages:

- User Needs Analysis and Design of Digital Tools
- Creation of the augmented reality software using Unity3D, Blender for modeling, and Vuforia for the development of augmented reality and indicators
- Evaluation and testing of the application with 120 students from three middle schools in Padang

The results of the study showed that the VirGO application, based on augmented reality, has three main advantages:

- It provides realistic visualization of the details of objects and educational materials.
- It offers interactivity through advanced video, image, and animation features.
- It increases students' interest in learning mathematics and reduces the sense of boredom (Syafril et al., 2021).

5.4. Artificial Intelligence

The research conducted by Erica Melis and her collaborators focuses on the development and evaluation of **ActiveMath**, an intelligent mathematical educational system that uses artificial intelligence and semantic technologies to offer personalized learning support. The first study, published in 2004, presents *ActiveMath* as an innovative teaching system. *ActiveMath* adapts exercises and explanations based on the needs and abilities of the students, offering interactive exercises and automated feedback. The study showed that *ActiveMath* can improve students' learning experience and enhance their mathematical skills compared to traditional teaching methods. The second study, published in 2001, expands on the description of *ActiveMath* as a general and adaptive online learning environment. The system offers a wide range of mathematical content and uses artificial intelligence to adapt the material to students' needs. Students can interact with the environment online and receive personalized exercises and feedback. The results of the study showed that *ActiveMath* is a flexible and effective tool for improving students' mathematical skills. The third study, published in 2006, focuses on the semantically aware components and services of *ActiveMath*. This study describes how the use of semantic technology improves the system's adaptability and accuracy. The semantically aware components allow the system to better understand mathematical content and adapt the teaching more precisely to the student's needs. The results showed that using semantic technologies enhances the learning experience and mathematical performance of students, making *ActiveMath* an advanced and effective learning tool. *ActiveMath* uses XML for mathematical documents and OMDoc, an extension of the OpenMath standard for mathematical symbols and expressions, for encoding its content. This teaching system could be used for distance learning, homework, or teacher-supported instruction. Overall, these three studies highlight the innovation and effectiveness of *ActiveMath* as an intelligent mathematical teaching system that uses artificial intelligence and semantic technologies to provide personalized learning support. The studies show that *ActiveMath* can significantly improve students' mathematical skills and enhance the learning experience through the use of advanced technologies (Erica et al., 2004; Erica et al., 2001; Erica et al., 2006).

Anthony and his collaborators (2008) proposed a prototype system based on intelligent teaching systems for solving algebraic equations by students. The system designers were inspired by the idea that handwritten data input could lead to better results than typing. The recognizer used was the **Freehand Formula Entry System (FFES)**. To train the recognizer, the researchers collected data from over 40 high school and middle school students in algebra, to ensure that the recognizer could adapt to various forms of handwriting. The study conducted to evaluate this project showed that students who entered mathematical equations via handwriting were faster and less prone to errors than those who typed. Of the 46 students who participated, over 80% stated that they preferred handwriting (Drigas et al., 2016).

5.5. Mobile Applications

According to a study by Kubier (2019), iPad applications such as **Garden of Numbers**, **Learn Numbers**, and **Learn Math** can be used for primary school students with learning difficulties, especially those with dyscalculia. The study was conducted in schools in the Rafha district of Saudi Arabia, with 38 students participating. The students attended 28 sessions, lasting 40 minutes, four times a week, focusing on memorizing number sequences, understanding mathematical operations, and distinguishing mathematical symbols. The students were divided into two groups: one group used the iPad applications, and the other followed the regular classroom curriculum. The results showed that students who used the iPad applications experienced significant reductions in dyscalculia compared to the control group that followed the regular curriculum (Kubier, 2019).

The study by O'Malley et al. used the **Math Racer** app by i4software on iPads to improve numeracy skills in students with moderate to severe cognitive disabilities, including those on the autism spectrum and with multiple disabilities. The study was conducted at a special school in Maryland with ten 7th and 8th-grade students. The students completed timed math exercises for addition and subtraction, with results automatically recorded. The study lasted for four weeks and showed that students solved more math problems correctly per minute while using the app compared to using paper and pencil. They also showed increased interest and engagement when using the iPads (O'Malley et al., 2013).

Dr. Nagavalli and her collaborators mention two popular iPad apps that help children with dyscalculia. The **MathBoard** app is suitable for preschool children with simple addition and subtraction problems and for elementary school students with multiplication, division, squares, cubes, and square root problems.

The **Long Division** app allows students to study and practice the method of long division, solving problems step by step (Drigas et al., 2016).

Kiger, Dani Herro, and Deb Prunty conducted a study to assess the impact of a mobile intervention on third-grade students' math performance. The study involved 87 students from an elementary school in the Midwest United States, divided into an intervention group and a comparison group. The intervention group used iPod Touch devices with math apps (**Multiplication Genius Lite, Mad Math Lite, Flash To Pass, Math Drills Lite, Math Tappers: Multiples, Multiplication Flashcards To Go, Brain Thaw, Math Magic, FlowMath**), while the comparison group followed traditional learning methods. Students in the intervention group showed significant improvement in solving multiplication problems, outperforming the comparison group. The study concluded that the use of mobile devices can enhance numeracy fluency and student engagement, providing an effective and cost-efficient solution for education. The study emphasized the need for further research on the long-term effects of mobile learning in different educational settings (Kiger et al., 2012).

The two mobile applications, **Go Play Ball** and **Go Road Trip**, are part of the **GoMath! Mobile** project aimed at school-age children and their families. They provide mathematical activities that can be performed during everyday activities. **Go Play Ball** allows users to record their performance in softball or baseball and view graphs or charts with their stats and the stats of their favorite professional players. Six families from Boston used the app for 3-4 weeks during the baseball season. **Go Road Trip** includes nine math games designed to encourage mathematical discussion during family road trips. Seven families with middle school students tested the app while traveling by car. The project was successful, as participants were able to use the mobile platform anytime and anywhere during fun activities, while simultaneously enhancing their social interactions (Drigas et al., 2016).

6. Conclusion

Addressing dyscalculia requires a combined approach that includes early diagnosis, personalized intervention, and the use of technologies such as software and digital games to enhance students' mathematical skills. The integration of ICT in education offers dynamic and effective solutions for students with learning difficulties, boosting their self-esteem and motivation to learn. Specifically, the use of digital tools and interactive environments such as virtual reality games, educational software, and mobile applications can significantly improve the mathematical skills of children with dyscalculia.

Compliance with ethical standards

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The Authors proclaim no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Papadopoulou, M. T., Karageorgiou, E., Kechayas, P., Geronikola, N., Lytridis, C., Bazinas, C., Kourampa, E., Avramidou, E., Kaburlasos, V. G., & Evangeliou, A. E. (2022). Efficacy of a robot-assisted intervention in improving learning performance of elementary school children with specific learning disorders. *Children*, 9(8), 1155. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children9081155>
- [2] Chaidi, I., Kefalis, C., Papagerasimou, I., & Drigas, A. (2021). Educational robotics in Primary Education: A case in Greece. *Research Society and Development*, 10, 1-12. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v10i9.16371>
- [3] Papadaki, A., & Karagianni, E. (2023). Intervention on my LD Learner's Spelling and Writing Difficulties through spelling instruction and ICTs. *World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences*, 09(01), 342-357. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjaets.2023.9.1.0182>
- [4] Mikropoulos, T., Kazakou, M., Soulis, S., & Morfidi, E. (2011). Phonological awareness software for dyslexic children. *Themes in Science and Technology Education*, 4, 35-54. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267331599_Phonological_Awareness_Software_for_Dyslexic_Children#fullTextFileContent
- [5] T. O'Connell, G. Freed and M. Rothberg, Using Apple technology to support learning for students with sensory and learning disabilities. Retrieved December, 12, 2011
- [6] Doğan, S., & Delialioğlu, Ö. (2020). A systematic review on the use of technology in learning disabilities. *Ankara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Fakültesi Özel Eğitim Dergisi*, 21, 611-638. <https://doi.org/10.21565/ozelegitimdergisi.563763>
- [7] Lyon, G., Shaywitz, S., & Shaywitz, B. (2003). A definition of dyslexia. *Annals of Dyslexia*, 53(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11881-003-0001-9>
- [8] Sung, E., & Mayer, R. E. (2013). Online multimedia learning with mobile devices and desktop computers: An experimental test of Clark's methods-not-media hypothesis. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(3), 639-647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2012.10.022>
- [9] Skiada, R., Soroniati, E., Gardeli, A., & Zissis, D. (2014). EasyLexia: A mobile application for children with learning difficulties. *Procedia Computer Science*, 27, 218-228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2014.02.025>
- [10] Athanasakou, S. (2023). The attitudes, perceptions, and skills of preschool teachers regarding the integration of ICT in classroom teaching (Master's thesis). University of Western Attica. Retrieved from <https://polynoe.lib.uniwa.gr/xmlui/handle/11400/3868>
- [11] Athanasiou, A. (2020). Teachers' perceptions regarding the use of new technologies in the teaching process. *Panhellenic Conference of Educational Sciences*, 8, 8-20. <https://doi.org/10.12681/educsc.2650>
- [12] Al-Wabil, A., Zaphiris, P., & Wilson, S. (2007). Web navigation for individuals with dyslexia: An exploratory study. In *Universal Access in Human Computer Interaction: Coping with Diversity* (Vol. 4554, pp. 593-602). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-73279-2_66
- [13] Alexandri, S., Gerakaki, S., Grigoriadou, A., Protopapas, A., Skaloubakas, Ch., & Tsagaraki, Ch. (2006). Software for automated identification of elementary school students with potential special learning difficulties: Development and implementation. In *Proceedings of the 5th Panhellenic Conference of ICT in Education "Information and Communication Technologies in Education"*, Thessaloniki, October 5-8, 2006.
- [14] Alexandropoulou, V., Anagnostopoulou, P., Drigas, A., Lorentzou, G., Lykothanasi, A., & Ntaountaki, P. (2019). Robotics in autism intervention. *International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT (iJES)*, 7, 4-17. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v7i4.11448>
- [15] Alexandropoulou, V., & Drigas, A. (2020). Specialization in ICTs and special education: Psychopedagogy of integration. Postgraduate program: Strengthening executive functions in children with special educational needs through mobile phone applications.
- [16] Alzoubi, A. (2023). The effect of using mobile applications in treating learning difficulties among students in Jordan. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies (ijIM)**, 17(22), 54-57. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v17i22.43659>

- [17] American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed.). Arlington, VA: American Psychiatric Publishing
- [18] Anagnostopoulou, P., & Drigas, A. (2020). ICTs, mindfulness and emotional intelligence in international educational policies. *International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT (ijES)*, 8(4). <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v8i4.18543>
- [19] Apostolopoulos, N. (2022, July 5). Educational software "Ensfimómata". *Blogs.sch.gr*. Retrieved from <https://blogs.sch.gr/apotoglou/2022/07/05/ekpaideytiko-logismiko-quot-ensfinomata-quot/>
- [20] Vathrakogianni, M., Pitsadioti, P., & Chalioti, V. (2020). Information and communication technologies in special education. *Panhellenic Conference of Educational Sciences*, 8, 47–57. <https://doi.org/10.12681/educ.2654>
- [21] Bakola, L., Drigas, A., & Skianis, C. (2022). Emotional intelligence vs. artificial intelligence: The interaction of human intelligence in evolutionary robotics. *Research Society and Development*, 11, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v11i16.36919>
- [22] Berger, M., Yule, W. & Rutter, M. (1975). Attainment and adjustment in two geographic areas: II. The prevalence of specific reading retardation. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 126, 510-519.
- [23] Berger, M., Yule, W., & Rutter, M. (1975). Attainment and adjustment in two geographic areas: II. The prevalence of specific reading retardation. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 126, 510-519.
- [24] Boder, E. (1973). Developmental dyslexia: A diagnostic approach based on three atypical reading-spelling patterns. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, 15(5), 663-687.
- [25] Bradley, R. H., & Corwyn, R. F. (2002). Socioeconomic status and child development. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 53(1), 371-399.
- [26] Bravou, V., & Drigas, A. (2019). A contemporary view on online and web tools for students with sensory & learning disabilities. *International Journal of Online Engineering (ijOE)*, 15, 97-104. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v15i12.10833>
- [27] Butterworth, B. (2003). *Dyscalculia Screener: Highlighting pupils with specific learning difficulties in maths (Age 6–14 years)*. London: nferNelson Publishing Company Limited. Retrieved from https://books.google.gr/books/about/Dyscalculia_Screener.html?id=EAMrAAAACAAJ&redir_esc=y
- [28] Butterworth, B., & Laurillard, D. (2010). Low numeracy and dyscalculia: Identification and intervention. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 42, 527-539. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-010-0267-4>
- [29] Giannopoulou, K. (2021). Parents' and secondary education students' views on distance education before and after using assistive technology for dyslexia (Master's thesis). School of Social and Human Sciences and Arts, Department of Educational and Social Policy, Postgraduate Program in Educational Sciences and Lifelong Learning, University of Patras, Greece
- [30] C. Lai, R. P. McMahan, M. Kitagawa, and I. Connolly, "Geometry Explorer: Facilitating Geometry Education with Virtual Reality," in *International Conference on Virtual, Augmented and Mixed Reality*, pp. 702–713, 2016. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-39907-2_67
- [31] Chaidi, I., Kefalis, C., Papagerasimou, I., & Drigas, A. (2021). Educational robotics in Primary Education: A case in Greece. *Research Society and Development*, 10, 1-12. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v10i9.16371>
- [32] D. Kiger, D. Herro and D. Prunty, Examining the influence of a mobile learning intervention on third grade math achievement. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 45(1), 2012, pp. 61–82
- [33] Di Lieto, M. C., Castro, E., Pecini, C., Inguaggiato, E., Cecchi, F., Dario, P., Cioni, G., & Sgandurra, G. (2020). Improving Executive Functions at School in Children With Special Needs by Educational Robotics. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 2813. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02813>
- [34] Gountakou, M.-I. (2019). Difficulties in acquiring spelling in Greek-speaking students with dyslexia while learning English as a second language (Master's thesis). Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Faculty of Philosophy, Department of Italian Language and Literature, Postgraduate Program "Language and Culture Sciences," Specialization: Language Disorders and Educational Intervention.
- [35] Diamantaki, K., Davou, M., & Panousis, G. (2001). *New technologies and old fears in the school system*. Athens: Papazisis.

- [36] Drigas, A. (2014). ICTs, mobile learning and social media to enhance learning for attention difficulties. Academia.edu. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/94036000/ICTs_Mobile_Learning_and_Social_Media_to_Enhance_Learning_for_Attention_Difficulties?sm=b
- [37] Drigas, A., & Dourou, A. (2013). A review on ICTs, e-learning and artificial intelligence for dyslexic's assistance. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)*, 8, 63-67. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v8i4.2980>
- [38] Drigas, A., & Kakoura, E.. (2023). Digital tools for children with reading difficulties. *World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences*, 14, 129-136. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjpbphs.2023.14.3.0252>
- [39] Drigas, A., Mitsea, E., & Skianis, C. (2023). Effects of digital games training on hormonal responses and brain plasticity. *Research Society and Development*, 12, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v12i2.39568>
- [40] Drigas, A., Pappas, M. & Lytras, M. (2016). Emerging technologies for ICT based education for dyscalculia: Implications for computer engineering education. 32. 1604-1610.
- [41] Drigas, A., Pappas, M. & Polychroni, F.. (2019). Assessment of mathematics difficulties for second and third graders: Cognitive and psychological parameters. *Behavioral Sciences*, 9, 76. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs9070076>
- [42] Drigas, A. & Politi-Georgousi, S. (2020). Mobile applications, an emerging powerful tool for dyslexia screening and intervention: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies (IJIM)*, 14, 4-17. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v14i18.15315>
- [43] Drigas, A. & Souliou, P.(2021). Specialization in ICTs and special education: Psychopedagogy of integration. Postgraduate program: Emotional intelligence and learning disabilities in preschool.
- [44] Exarchou, P. (2012). Use of software programs for the diagnosis and treatment of learning difficulties in preschool and school age (Bachelor's thesis). University of Epirus
- [45] Ellis, A. W. (2016). *Reading, Writing and Dyslexia: A Cognitive Analysis*. Hove: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- [46] Conference Editorial. (2022, March 18). 11th Panhellenic and International Conference "ICT in Education." Publisher. ISBN: 978-618-83186-2-5.
- [47] epikoinonia_7pbkra. (2023, 17 Σεπτεμβρίου). Μαθησιακές δυσκολίες (Συμπτώματα και διάγνωση) Μέρος 1ο. Ανακτήθηκε από <https://epikoinonia.net/%CE%BC%CE%B1%CE%B8%CE%B7%CF%83%CE%B9%CE%B1%CE%BA%CE%AD%CF%82-%CE%B4%CF%85%CF%83%CE%BA%CE%BF%CE%BB%CE%AF%CE%B5%CF%82-%CF%83%CF%85%CE%BC%CF%80%CF%84%CF%8E%CE%BC%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%B1-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%B9/>
- [48] Erica Melis and Jorg Siekmann : *ActiveMath: An Intelligent Tutoring System for Mathematics*, *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 3070, 2004, pp 91–101.39.
- [49] Erica Melis, Eric Andres, Jochen Budenbender, Adrian Frischauf, George Goduadze, et al.. *ActiveMath: A Generic and Adaptive Web-Based Learning Environment*. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education* , 2001, 12, σσ.385-407. (hal-00197329)
- [50] Erica Melis, Giorgi Gogvadze, Martin Homik, Paul Libbrecht, Carsten Ullrich and Stefan Winterstein.(2006). *Semantic-aware components and services of ActiveMath*, *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 37(3), 2006, pp. 405–423
- [51] Felani, K. (2022). Utilization of ICT, prerequisites for their successful use in secondary education, and teachers' views on their implementation (Master's thesis). University of Piraeus. Retrieved from <https://dione.lib.unipi.gr/xmlui/handle/unipi/14146>
- [52] Galitskaya, V., & Drigas, A. (2020). Special Education: Teaching Geometry with ICTs. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)*, 15, Article 173. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i06.11242>
- [53] Galitskaya, V., & Drigas, A. (2023). Mobiles & ICT Based Interventions for Learning Difficulties in Geometry. *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (IJEP)*, 13, 21-36. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v13i4.36309>
- [54] Geschwind, N. (1970). The organization of language and the brain. *Science*, 170(3961), 940-944.

- [55] Ginsburg, H., Jamalain, A., & Creighan, S. (2013). Cognitive guidelines for the design and evaluation of early mathematics software: The example of MathemAntics. Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-6440-8_6
- [56] Gregor, P., Dickinson, A., Macaffer, A., & Andreasen, P. (2003). SeeWord - A personal word processing environment for dyslexic computer users. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8535.00331>
- [57] Guha, S. (2003). Are we all technically prepared? Teachers' perspective on the causes of comfort or discomfort in using computers at elementary grade teaching. *Information Technology in Childhood Education Annual*, 2003.
- [58] Hammill, D. D. (1990). On defining learning disabilities: An emerging consensus. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 23(2), 74-84.
- [59] Hargreaves, A., & Fullan, M. (1992). *Understanding Teacher Development*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- [60] Hargreaves, A., & Fullan, M. (1992). *Understanding Teacher Development*. Teachers College Press.
- [61] Hattingh, M. J., & Smith, C. (2020, November). Assistive technologies for students with dyslexia: A systematic literature review. In *Innovative Technologies and Learning* (pp. xx-xx). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-63885-6_55
- [62] Honey, M. (1990). Teachers' beliefs and technology integration: Different understandings. Technical Report No. 90-8. Center for Technology in Education.
- [63] Honey, M., & Moeller, B. (1990). Teachers' beliefs and technology integration: Different beliefs, different actions. Technical report, Center for Technology in Education, Bank Street College of Education.
- [64] Hung, Pi-Hsia & Su, I-Hsiang. (2010). Applying affective assessment to detect the ICT infused mathematics intervention effect. *CAR 2010 - 2010 2nd International Asia Conference on Informatics in Control, Automation and Robotics*. 2. 321 - 323. [10.1109/CAR.2010.5456537](https://doi.org/10.1109/CAR.2010.5456537).
- [65] iMommy. (2012, Οκτώβριος 18). Μαθησιακές δυσκολίες. Ανακτήθηκε από <https://www.imommy.gr/2012/10/18/mathhsiak-es-dyskolies/>
- [66] Ινστιτούτο Εκπαιδευτικής Πολιτικής. (2022). Στρογγυλά με Αξία. Ανάκτηση από <https://prosvasimo.iep.edu.gr/el/gia-mathites-me-metria-kai-elafria-nohtikh-anaphria/strogila-me-aksia>
- [67] J. L. Rodríguez, I. Romero, and A. Codina, "The Influence of NeoTrie VR's Immersive Virtual Reality on the Teaching and Learning of Geometry," *Mathematics*, vol. 9, no. 19, p. 2411, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9192411>
- [68] Jamali, H. R., Nicholas, D., & Williams, P. (2006, July). Using ICT with people with special education needs: What the literature tells us. *Aslib Proceedings*, 58(4), 330-345. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00012530610687704>
- [69] Kafai, Y. B., & Resnick, M. (Eds.). (2002). *Constructionism in Practice: Designing, Thinking, and Learning in a Digital World*. Routledge.
- [70] Kafai, Y. B., Ching, C. C., & Marshall, S. K. (2002). Children as designers of educational multimedia software. *Computers & Education*, 29(1-2), 117-126.
- [71] Kálózi-Szabó, C., Mohai, K., & Cottini, M. (2022). Employing Robotics in Education to Enhance Cognitive Development—A Pilot Study. *Sustainability*, 14(15951). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142315951>
- [72] Karagianni, E., & Drigas, A. (2023). New Technologies for Inclusive Learning for Students with Special Educational Needs. *International Journal of Online and Biomedical Engineering (ijOE)*, 19, 4-21. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v19i05.36417>
- [73] Karvounis, M. (2007). "Learning and psychological support for children with learning difficulties in the classroom," in Makri-Botsari, E. (Ed.), *Issues in Classroom Problem Management (Vol. A)*. Athens: Pedagogical Institute. pp. 72-83.
- [74] Karkouli, M. (2021). 4th Industrial Revolution: Digital Transformation and the Greek Educational System. Challenges and Opportunities. The views of primary school teachers (Master's thesis). Hellenic Open University. Retrieved from <https://apothesis.eap.gr/archive/item/154697>
- [75] Kasimati, K., & Yalamas, V. (2001). Teachers' views on the contribution of new technologies to the educational process, *Review of Educational Issues*, 114-127.
- [76] Kirk, S. A. (1962). Diagnosis and remediation of learning disabilities. *Exceptional Children*, 29*(2), 73-78.

- [77] Kirschner, P. A., Sweller, J., & Clark, R. E. (2006). Why minimal guidance during instruction does not work: An analysis of the failure of constructivist, discovery, problem-based, experiential, and inquiry-based teaching. *Educational Psychologist*, 41(2), 75-86. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326985ep4102_1
- [78] Kubier, A. A. H. (2019). The effectiveness of using some iPad applications to reduce dyscalculia among a sample of students with learning disabilities in Rafha Province. *Journal of Organizational Behavior Research*, 4(2), 283-298.
- [79] Kumar, R. (2009, April). Convergence of ICT and Education. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242589222_Convergence_of_ICT_and_Education
- [80] Komis, V. (2004). *Information and Communication Technologies in Education*. Kritiki Publications.
- [81] Karamani, E. (2021, February 13). Detection of learning difficulties: When does it happen? Which tests are used? KE.PSY.PE. Retrieved from <https://kepsype.gr/news/anichneusi-mathisiakon-diskolion-pote-ginetai-poia-test-chrisimopoiountai>
- [82] Komis, V. (2004). *Introduction to Educational Applications of Information and Communication Technologies*. Athens: New Technologies Publications.
- [83] Komis, V. (2004). *Introduction to Applications of ICT in Education*. Athens: New Technologies Publications.
- [84] Korelis, I. (2023). Enhancement of mathematical education for students with learning difficulties and disabilities: The role of ICT (Master's thesis). University of Western Attica. Retrieved from <https://polynoe.lib.uniwa.gr/xmlui/handle/11400/4609>
- [85] Kourkoutas, H. (1978). *Learning difficulties and mental disorders*. Patakis Publications.
- [86] Koutsileoua, S. K. (2015). Evaluation of the effectiveness of teacher training in Attica on the pedagogical use of Information and Communication Technologies. National Technical University of Athens. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10797/14903>
- [87] Metta, G., & Skordialos, E. (2020). Learning difficulties, types, and educational intervention. *Panhellenic Conference of Educational Sciences*, 8, 707–720. <https://doi.org/10.12681/educ.2716>
- [88] Metta, G., & Skordialos, E. (2020). Learning difficulties, types, and educational intervention. *Panhellenic Conference of Educational Sciences*, 8, 707–720. <https://doi.org/10.12681/educ.2716>
- [89] Balioukas, G. (2023). Special education teachers' perceptions on the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in Special Education Schools (S.M.E.A.E.) (Master's thesis). University of Peloponnese. Retrieved from https://amitos.library.uop.gr/xmlui/bitstream/handle/123456789/7182/Balioukas_6062202003042.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- [90] Xesternou, M., & Iliopoulou, M. (2007). Software "The Verb Train," Teaching of Ancient Greek verb conjugation. Why it constitutes an appropriate learning environment for dyslexic students. 4th Conference, Syros. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/7148003/Ξέστερνου_M_and_Ιλιοπούλου_M_2007_Λογισμικό_Το_Τρενάκι_των_Πημάτων_Διδασκαλία_της_κλίσης_των_ρημάτων_της_αρχαίας_ελληνικής_γλώσσας_Γιατί_αποτελεί_κατάλληλο_περιβάλλον_μάθησης_για_μαθητές_που_παρουσιάζουν_δυσλεξία
- [91] Lampropoulos, Georgios & Keramopoulos, Euclid & Diamantaras, Kostas & Evangelidis, Georgios. (2022). Augmented Reality and Gamification in Education: A Systematic Literature Review of Research, Applications, and Empirical Studies. *Applied Sciences*. 12. 6809. [10.3390/app12136809](https://doi.org/10.3390/app12136809).
- [92] Lepicnik Vodopivec, Jurka & Bagon, Špela. (2016). Motivation for Using ICT and Pupils with Learning Difficulties. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (ijET)*. 11. 70. [10.3991/ijet.v11i10.5786](https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v11i10.5786).
- [93] Lerner, J. W. & Johns, B. (2009). *Learning Disabilities and Related Disabilities: Strategies for Success*, 11th Edition, Stamford: Cengage Learning.
- [94] Lonstrup, J., Denager, T., & Christensen, M. B. (2012). Enhancement of 7th-10th graders' understanding of equations with tangible representations. In *Proceedings of the 2012 IDC Conference*. Retrieved from https://www.cse.chalmers.se/research/group/idc/ituniv/sider12/wp-content/uploads/lonstrup_et_al_paper.pdf
- [95] Maitrei, Kohli & Prasad, T.. (2010). Identifying Dyslexic Students by Using Artificial Neural Networks. *Lecture Notes in Engineering and Computer Science*. 2183. 118.

- [96] Manghirmalani, P., More, D., & Jain, K. (2012). A fuzzy approach to classify learning disability. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Artificial Intelligence (IJARAI)*, 1(2), 1-8. Retrieved from https://thesai.org/Downloads/IJARAI/Volume1No2/Paper_1-A_Fuzzy_Approach_to_Classify_Learning_Disability.pdf
- [97] Manghirmalani, P., More, D., & Jain, K. (2012). A fuzzy approach to classify learning disability. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Artificial Intelligence (IJARAI)*, 1(2), 1-8. Retrieved from https://thesai.org/Downloads/IJARAI/Volume1No2/Paper_1-A_Fuzzy_Approach_to_Classify_Learning_Disability.pdf
- [98] Mikropoulos, T., Kazakou, M., Soulis, S., & Morfidi, E. (2011). Phonological awareness software for dyslexic children. *Themes in Science and Technology Education*, 4, 35-54. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267331599_Phonological_Awareness_Software_for_Dyslexic_Children#fullTextFileContent
- [99] Mouzaki, A. & Sideridis, G. (2007). Poor readers profiles among Greek students of elementary school. *Hellenic Journal of Psychology*, 4, 205-232.
- [100] Mouzaki, A., & Sideridis, G. (2007). Poor readers' profiles among Greek students of elementary school. *Hellenic Journal of Psychology*, 4, 205-232.
- [101] O'Malley, S. Jenkins, B. Wesley, C. Donehower, D. Rabuck and M. E. B. Lewis, Effectiveness of Using iPadsto Build Math Fluency, Online Submission, 2013
- [102] Paidagogiko.gr. (n.d.). Evaluation of learning ability. Retrieved from <https://paidagogiko.gr/blog/aksiologisi-tis-mathisiakiss-ikanotitas>
- [103] Palacios, Ana & Sanchez, Luciano & Couso, Inés. (2010). Diagnosis of dyslexia with low quality data with genetic fuzzy systems. *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning*. 51. 993-1009. 10.1016/j.ijar.2010.07.008.
- [104] Panteliadou, S. (2004). The mapping of the special education field. Presentation at the seminar "Mapping – Special Education Curriculum" by the Pedagogical Institute, EPEAEK – Ministry of National Education and Religious Affairs, April 25, 2004, Thessaloniki.
- [105] Papadaki, A., & Karagianni, E. (2023). Intervention on my LD Learner's Spelling and Writing Difficulties through spelling instruction and ICTs. *World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences*, 09(01), 342-357. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjaets.2023.9.1.0182>
- [106] Papadimitriou, P. (2022). Response to teaching and intervention for the detection and treatment of learning difficulties in mathematics (Doctoral dissertation). University of Thessaly. <https://doi.org/10.12681/eadd/51228>
- [107] Papadopoulou, M. T., Karageorgiou, E., Kechayas, P., Geronikola, N., Lytridis, C., Bazinas, C., Kourampa, E., Avramidou, E., Kaburlasos, V. G., & Evangeliou, A. E. (2022). Efficacy of a robot-assisted intervention in improving learning performance of elementary school children with specific learning disorders. *Children*, 9(8), 1155. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children9081155>
- [108] Pekka Ra'sa'nena, Jonna Salminen, Anna J. Wilson, Pirjo Aunio, Stanislas Dehaene: Computer-assisted intervention for children with low numeracy skills, *Cognitive Development*, 24, 2009, pp. 450–472 DOI: 10.1016/j.cogdev.2009.09.003
- [109] Pelgrum, W. J. (2001). Obstacles to the integration of ICT in education: Results from a worldwide educational assessment. *Computers & Education*, 37(2), 163-178. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1315\(01\)00045-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-1315(01)00045-8)
- [110] Peter Gregor. SeeWord - a personal word processing environment for dyslexic computer users. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 34(3), pp. 341-355, (2003)
- [111] Plerou, A., & Vlamos, P. (2013). Algorithmic problem solving using interactive virtual environment: A case study. In M. A. Orgun & J. Thornton (Eds.), *Intelligent Data Engineering and Automated Learning – IDEAL 2013: Lecture Notes in Computer Science* (Vol. 8206, pp. 383-390). Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-41013-0_45
- [112] Politis, P., Roussos, P., Karamanis, M., & Tsouosis, G. (2000). Evaluation of teacher training within the framework of the project ODYSSEAS, in V. Komis (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 2nd Panhellenic Conference "Information and Communication Technologies in Education"*, 583-592, Patras.

- [113] Polydouri, E. A. (2015, October). Development of teacher skills in special education for managing problems in students with complex cognitive, emotional, and social difficulties and their families (Master's thesis). University of Peloponnese.
- [114] Polychronopoulou, St. (2012-2013). Diagnosis, evaluation, and treatment of dyslexia [Course notes]. University of Athens. Retrieved from http://www.primedu.uoa.gr/fileadmin/primedu.uoa.gr/uploads/Pdfs/Proptyxiaka/Polyxronopoulou/SIMEIO_SEIS_GIA_TO_MATHIMA__Diagnosi_axiologisi_kai_antimetopisi_tis_dyslexias_.pdf
- [115] Protopapas, A., Skaloubakas, Ch., Gerakaki, S., Alexandri, S., Grigoriadou, A., & Tsagaraki, Ch. (2006). Software for automated identification of elementary school students with potential special learning difficulties: Development and implementation. In Proceedings of the 5th Panhellenic Conference of ICT in Education, Thessaloniki, October 5-8.
- [116] Räsänen, P., Salminen, J., Wilson, A. J., Aunio, P., & Dehaene, S. (2009). Computer-assisted intervention for children with low numeracy skills. *Cognitive Development*, 24, 450-472. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogdev.2009.09.003>
- [117] Raver, C. C. (2004). Placing emotional self-regulation in sociocultural and socioeconomic contexts. *Child Development*, 75(2), 346-353.
- [118] S. Syafril, Z. Asril, E. Engkizar, A. Zafirah, F. A. Agusti, & I. Sugiharta, Designing Prototype Model of Virtual Geometry in Mathematics Learning using AugmentedReality," in *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1796, no. 1, p. 012035, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1796/1/012035>
- [119] Silin, Y., & Kwok, D. (2016). A study of students' attitudes towards using ICT in a social constructivist environment. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 33, 1-15. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.2890>
- [120] Singleton, C. Fiona Simmons and Horne, J. Computerised screening for dyslexia in adults, *Journal of Research in Reading*, volume 32 (1), pp. 137-152. (2009). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9817.2008.01386.x>
- [121] Siouli, S., Makris, S., Romanopoulou, E., & Bamidis, P. P. D. (2020). Living with learning difficulties: Two case studies exploring the relationship between emotion and performance in students with learning difficulties. Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-57717-9_10
- [122] Skraparlis, Ch. (2022). ICT in the education of individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorders (Master's thesis). University of Western Macedonia & University of Piraeus.
- [123] Slaouti, D., & Barton, A. (2007). Opportunities for practice and development: Newly qualified teachers and the use of information and communications technologies in teaching foreign languages in English secondary school contexts. *Journal of In-Service Education*, 33(4), 405-424
- [124] Snowling, M. J., & Hulme, C. (2012). *The Science of Reading: A Handbook*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.
- [125] Spantidakis, G., Mouzaki, A., & Charoula, A. (2021). Methodology of design and development of educational software for students with learning difficulties: The example "In the Land of Lenou."
- [126] Stasinou, D. (1999). *Learning difficulties and education*. Athens: Dioptra Publications.
- [127] Synefiias, G. (2019). Epidemiological study of special educational needs in the student population of the Evia region (Master's thesis). National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, School of Health Sciences, Medical School. Retrieved from <https://pergamon.lib.uoa.gr/uoa/dl/object/2873332/file.pdf>
- [128] T. O'Connell, G. Freed and M. Rothberg, Using Apple technology to support learning for students with sensory and learning disabilities. Retrieved December, 12, 2011
- [129] Tziviniku, S. (2015). *Learning difficulties: Teaching interventions*. Greek Academic Libraries Association. National Technical University of Athens, Greek Academic Electronic Texts and Resources.
- [130] Tzimogiannis, A., & Komis, V. (2004). Attitudes and perceptions of secondary education teachers regarding the application of ICT in their teaching, in M. Grigoriadou (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 4th Panhellenic Conference with International Participation "Information and Communication Technologies in Education"*, Volume A, 165-176, Athens.
- [131] Tzouveli, P., Schmidt, A., Schneider, M., Symvonis, A., & Kollias, S. (2008). Adaptive reading assistance for the inclusion of students with dyslexia: The AGENT-DYSL approach. In *Proceedings of the 8th IEEE International*

Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies (ICALT 2008) (pp. 167-171). IEEE.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICALT.2008.236>

- [132] Triga-Mertika, E. (2010). Learning difficulties. General & special learning difficulties – Dyslexia. Athens: Grigori Publications.
- [133] Tsomboli, E.I. (2017). Learning difficulties – Dyscalculia. Panhellenic Conference of Educational Sciences, Vol. B, 2016(2), pp. 1308 – 1322. Source from <http://dx.doi.org/10.12681/educ.1011>
- [134] Williams, B. (2009). Investigating the effects of authentic learning practices in a higher education course: A mixed method approach. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 25(2), 177-193. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.1143>
- [135] Wilson AJ, Revkin SK, Cohen D, Cohen L, Dehaene S: An opentrial assessment of "The Number Race", an adaptive computergame for remediation of dyscalculia, *Behavioral and Brain Func-tions*, 2(20), (2006)
- [136] Wilson, A. J., Dehaene, S., Pinel, P., Revkin, S., Cohen, L., & Cohen, D. (2006). Principles underlying the design of "The Number Race", an adaptive computer game for remediation of dyscalculia. *Behavioral and Brain Functions*, 2, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1744-9081-2-19>
- [137] Wilson, A.J., Dehaene, S., Pinel1, P., Revkin, S.K., Cohenand L.and Cohen, D.: Principles underlying the design of "The NumberRace", an adaptive computer game for remediation of dyscalculia,*Behavioral and Brain Functions* , 2(19), (2006) doi: 10.1186/1744-9081-2-19
- [138] Woodfine, B.P. , Baptista Nunes, M., Wright, D.J. : ‘Text-basedSynchronous E-learning and Dyslexia: Not Necessarily thePerfect Match!’, *Computers & Education* 50, (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2006.08.010>
- [139] Y.-S. Su, H.-W. Cheng, and C.-F. Lai, “Study of Virtual Reality Immersive TechnologyEnhanced Mathematics Geometry Learning,” *Frontiers in Psychology* , vol. 13, 2022.<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.760418>
- [140] Zogopoulos, St. (2001). *New Technologies and Communication Tools in the Educational Process*. Kleidarithmos Publications.
- [141] Stathopoulou, et all 2018, Mobile assessment procedures for mental health and literacy skills in education. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 12(3), 21-37, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v12i3.8038>
- [142] Kokkalia G, AS Drigas, A Economou 2016 Mobile learning for preschool education. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies* 10 (4), 57-64 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v10i4.6021>
- [143] Stathopoulou A, Karabatzaki Z, Tsiros D, Katsantoni S, Drigas A, 2019 Mobile apps the educational solution for autistic students in secondary education , *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies* 13 (2), 89-101<https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v13i02.9896>
- [144] Drigas A, DE Dede, S Dedes 2020 Mobile and other applications for mental imagery to improve learning disabilities and mental health , *International Journal of Computer Science Issues (IJCSI)* 17 (4), 18-23, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.3987533
- [145] Drigas A, Petrova A 2014 ICTs in speech and language therapy , *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (ijEP)* 4 (1), 49-54 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v4i1.3280>
- [146] Bravou V, Oikonomidou D, Drigas A, 2022 Applications of Virtual Reality for Autism Inclusion. A review , *revista Retos* 45, 779-785 <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v45i0.92078>
- [147] Chaidi I, Drigas A, 2022 "Parents' views Questionnaire for the education of emotions in Autism Spectrum Disorder" in a Greek context and the role of ICTs , *Technium Social Sciences Journal* 33, 73-9, DOI:10.47577/tssj.v33i1.6878
- [148] Bravou V, Drigas A, 2019 A contemporary view on online and web tools for students with sensory & learning disabilities , *ijOE* 15(12) 97 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v15i12.10833>
- [149] Chaidi I, Drigas A, C Karagiannidis 2021 ICT in special education , *Technium Social Sciences Journal* 23, 187, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v23i1.4277>
- [150] Xanthopoulou M, Kokalia G, Drigas A, 2019, Applications for Children with Autism in Preschool and Primary Education. *Int. J. Recent Contributions Eng. Sci. IT* 7 (2), 4-16, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v7i2.10335>
- [151] Drigas AS, Koukianakis LG, Papagerasimou YV, 2005 A system for e-inclusion for individuals with sight disabilities *Wseas transactions on circuits and systems* 4 (11), 1776-1780

- [152] S Politi-Georgousi, A Drigas 2020 Mobile Applications, an Emerging Powerful Tool for Dyslexia Screening and Intervention: A Systematic Literature Review , International Association of Online Engineering
- [153] A Drigas, P Theodorou, 2016 ICTs and Music in Special Learning Disabilities, International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT (iJES), 4(3), pp. 12–16. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v4i3.6066>
- [154] Galitskaya, V., & Drigas, A. (2020). Special Education: Teaching Geometry with ICTs. International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET), 15(06), pp. 173–182. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i06.11242>
- [155] Moraiti, I. ., Fotoglou, A. ., Dona, K. ., Katsimperi, A. ., Tsionakas, K. ., & Drigas, A. (2022). IoT in Special Education. Technium Social Sciences Journal, 30(1), 55–63. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v30i1.6307>
- [156] Alexopoulou, A., Batsou, A., & Drigas, A. S. (2019). Effectiveness of Assessment, Diagnostic and Intervention ICT Tools for Children and Adolescents with ADHD. International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT (iJES), 7(3), pp. 51–63. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v7i3.11178>
- [157] Pergantis, P., & Drigas, A. (2023). Assistive technology for autism spectrum disorder children that experiences stress and anxiety. Brazilian Journal of Science, 2(12), 77–93. <https://doi.org/10.14295/bjs.v2i12.426>
- [158] Pergantis, P., & Drigas, A. (2023). Sensory integration therapy as enabler for developing emotional intelligence in children with autism spectrum disorder and the ICT's role. Brazilian Journal of Science, 2(12), 53–65. <https://doi.org/10.14295/bjs.v2i12.422>
- [159] Stathopoulou A, Spinou D, Driga AM, 2023, Burnout Prevalence in Special Education Teachers, and the Positive Role of ICTs , iJOE 19 (08), 19-37
- [160] Stathopoulou A, Spinou D, Driga AM, 2023, Working with Students with Special Educational Needs and Predictors of Burnout. The Role of ICTs. iJOE 19 (7), 39-51
- [161] Loukeri PI, Stathopoulou A, Driga AM, 2023 Special Education Teachers' Gifted Guidance and the role of Digital Technologies , TECH HUB 6 (1), 16-27
- [162] Stathopoulou A, Temekinidou M, Driga AM, Dimitriou 2022 Linguistic performance of Students with Autism Spectrum Disorders, and the role of Digital Technologies , Eximia 5 (1), 688-701
- [163] Vouglanis T, Driga AM 2023 Factors affecting the education of gifted children and the role of digital technologies. TechHub Journal 6, 28-39
- [164] Vouglanis T, Driga AM 2023 The use of ICT for the early detection of dyslexia in education , TechHub Journal 5, 54-67
- [165] Drakatos N, Tsompou E, Karabatzaki Z, Driga AM 2023 Virtual reality environments as a tool for teaching Engineering. Educational and Psychological issues , TechHub Journal 4, 59-76
- [166] Drakatos N, Tsompou E, Karabatzaki Z, Driga AM 2023 The contribution of online gaming in Engineering education , Eximia 8, 14-30
- [167] Drigas A, Vrettaros J, Tagoulis A, Kouremenos D, 2010 Teaching a foreign language to deaf people via vodcasting & web 2.0 tools World Summit on Knowledge Society, 514-521 DOI:10.1007/978-3-642-16324-1_60
- [168] Chaidi E, Kefalis C, Papagerasimou Y, Drigas, 2021, Educational robotics in Primary Education. A case in Greece , Research, Society and Development journal 10 (9), e17110916371-e17110916371, <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v10i9.16371>
- [169] Lytra N, Drigas A 2021 STEAM education-metacognition-Specific Learning Disabilities , Scientific Electronic Archives journal 14 (10) <https://doi.org/10.36560/141020211442>
- [170] Demertzi E, Voukelatos N, Papagerasimou Y, Drigas A, 2018 Online learning facilities to support coding and robotics courses for youth , International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (iJEP) 8 (3), 69-80, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v8i3.8044>
- [171] Drigas A, Kouremenos S, Vrettos S, Vrettaros J, Kouremenos S, 2004 An expert system for job matching of the unemployed , Expert Systems with Applications 26 (2), 217-224 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0957-4174\(03\)00136-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0957-4174(03)00136-2)
- [172] Pergantis, P., & Drigas, A. (2024). The effect of drones in the educational Process: A systematic review. Education Sciences, 14(6), 665. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14060665>

- [173] Chaidi I, Drigas A 2022 Digital games & special education , Technium Social Sciences Journal 34, 214-236 <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v34i1.7054>
- [174] Doulou A, Drigas A 2022 Electronic, VR & Augmented Reality Games for Intervention in ADHD , Technium Social Sciences Journal, 28, 159. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v28i1.5728>
- [175] Drigas A, Mitsea E, Skianis C 2021 The Role of Clinical Hypnosis & VR in Special Education , International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering Science & IT (iJES) 9(4), 4-18. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i4.26147>
- [176] V Galitskaya, A Drigas 2021 The importance of working memory in children with Dyscalculia and Ageometria , Scientific Electronic Archives journal 14 (10) <https://doi.org/10.36560/141020211449>
- [177] Drigas A, Karyotaki M 2019 Attention and its Role: Theories and Models. International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning 14 (12), 169-182, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v14i12.10185>
- [178] Drigas A, Mitsea E, Skianis C. 2022 Virtual Reality and Metacognition Training Techniques for Learning Disabilities , SUSTAINABILITY 14(16), 10170, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141610170>
- [179] Drigas A., Sideraki A. 2021 Emotional Intelligence in Autism , Technium Social Sciences Journal 26, 80, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v26i1.5178>
- [180] Drigas A, Mitsea E, Skianis C.. 2022 Subliminal Training Techniques for Cognitive, Emotional and Behavioural Balance. The role of Emerging Technologies , Technium Social Sciences Journal 33, 164-186, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v33i1.6881>
- [181] Bamicha V, Drigas A, 2022 The Evolutionary Course of Theory of Mind - Factors that facilitate or inhibit its operation & the role of ICTs , Technium Social Sciences Journal 30, 138-158, DOI:10.47577/tssj.v30i1.6220
- [182] Karyotaki M, Bakola L, Drigas A, Skianis C, 2022 Women's Leadership via Digital Technology and Entrepreneurship in business and society , Technium Social Sciences Journal. 28(1), 246-252. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v28i1.5907>
- [183] Drigas A, Bakola L, 2021The 8x8 Layer Model Consciousness-Intelligence-Knowledge Pyramid, and the Platonic Perspectives , International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT (iJES) 9(2) 57-72, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i2.22497>
- [184] Mitsea E, Drigas A., Skianis C, 2022 Breathing, Attention & Consciousness in Sync: The role of Breathing Training, Metacognition & Virtual Reality , Technium Social Sciences Journal 29, 79-97, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v29i1.6145>
- [185] Mitsea E, Drigas A, Skianis C, 2022 ICTs and Speed Learning in Special Education: High-Consciousness Training Strategies for High-Capacity Learners through Metacognition Lens , Technium Social Sciences Journal 27, 230, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v27i1.5599>
- [186] Drigas A, Karyotaki M, Skianis C, 2017 Success: A 9 layered-based model of giftedness , International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT 5(4) 4-18, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v5i4.7725>
- [187] Drigas A, Mitsea E, Skianis C, 2022 Intermittent Oxygen Fasting and Digital Technologies: from Antistress and Hormones Regulation to Wellbeing, Bliss and Higher Mental States , Technium BioChemMed journal 3 (2), 55-73
- [188] Drigas A, Mitsea E 2022 Conscious Breathing: a Powerful Tool for Physical & Neuropsychological Regulation. The role of Mobile Apps , Technium Social Sciences Journal 28, 135-158. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v28i1.5922>
- [189] Drigas A, Mitsea E 2021 Neuro-Linguistic Programming & VR via the 8 Pillars of Metacognition X 8 Layers of Consciousness X 8 Intelligences , Technium Social Sciences Journal 26(1), 159-176. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v26i1.5273>
- [190] Drigas A, Mitsea E, Skianis C 2021. The Role of Clinical Hypnosis and VR in Special Education , International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering Science & IT (IJES) 9(4), 4-17.
- [191] E Mitsea, A Drigas, C Skianis 2022 Metacognition in Autism Spectrum Disorder: Digital Technologies in Metacognitive Skills Training , Technium Social Sciences Journal, 153-173
- [192] Kontostavrou, E. Z., & Drigas, A. (2021). How Metacognition Supports Giftedness in Leadership: A Review of Contemporary Literature. , International Journal of Advanced Corporate Learning (iJAC), 14(2), pp. 4-16. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijac.v14i2.23237>

- [193] Vouglanis T, Driga A M, Drigas A 2022 Charismatic Children: Heredity, Environment and ICTs , Technium Sustainability journal 2,5 1-15<https://doi.org/10.47577/sustainability.v2i5.7378>
- [194] Chaidi, I. , & Drigas, A. (2022). Social and Emotional Skills of children with ASD: Assessment with Emotional Comprehension Test (TEC) in a Greek context and the role of ICTs. , Technium Social Sciences Journal, 33(1), 146–163. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v33i1.6857>
- [195] Vouglanis, T. , Driga, A. M., & Drigas, A. (2022). Physical and mental exercise to create new congenial neurons, to increase intelligence and the role of ICTs. , Technium BioChemMed journal, 3(3), 21–36. <https://doi.org/10.47577/biochemmed.v3i3.7325>
- [196] Chaidi, I. , & Drigas, A. (2022). Emotional intelligence and learning, and the role of ICTs. Technium Social Sciences Journal, 35(1), 56–78. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v35i1.7249>
- [197] Pergantis, P.; Bamicha, V.; Chaidi, I.; Drigas, A. Driving Under Cognitive Control: The Impact of Executive Functions in Driving. World Electric Vehicle Journal 2024, 15, 474, doi:10.3390/wevj15100474.
- [198] Pergantis, P. Developmental Coordination Disorder and the Role of New Technologies as Intervention Tool. World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews 2023, 19, 519–528, doi:10.30574/wjarr.2023.19.1.1333.
- [199] Drigas A, Papoutsi C, Skianis C, Being an Emotionally Intelligent Leader through the Nine-Layer Model of Emotional Intelligence-The Supporting Role of New Technologies, Sustainability MDPI 15 (10), 1-18